

ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS) THROUGH EFFECTIVE BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN SOUTH-EAST STATES OF NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *This study was carried out to determine strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A survey research design was used for the study. The population for the study consisted of 80 Business Educators from federal and state universities in South-East states. There was no sampling since the population was not too large. A-24 items structured Questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from the Department of mathematics and computer Education (measurement and Evaluation), all from Enugu state university of science and Technology. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the two sections of the instrument and they are 0.66 and 0.70; while the reliability coefficient of the whole instrument gave a value of 0.76. Mean with standard deviation was used to answer the research questions; while the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 78 degree of freedom was tested with t-test statistics. Findings showed that institutional and lecturers-related strategies are needed to achieve sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in south-East state. Again, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State-owned universities on institutional and lecturers-related strategies respectively for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that, there should be constant review of Business Education curriculum to meet global goals. Again, Regular conferences should be organized to the stakeholders based on SDGs.*

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Business Education, Achievement

Introduction

It is the duty of any responsible government irrespective of the level, to provide her citizens with democratic dividends. Globally, citizens seem to be facing hunger, insecurity, unemployment, poor health-care among others. In an attempt to overcome these challenges, in September 2015, 193 countries came together at United Nations to adopt comprehensive strategy to tackle challenges related to global sustainable development (eetbusinessschool.org)

Sustainable Development according to Salami (2019), is a development for today without compromising the gains of tomorrow. Salami further stated that, it is ability to manage, to withstand and continue in spite of any prevailing circumstances and not solely economic growth or human development but both. Hence sustainable Development must ensure remarkable quality of life which is the degree of well-being felt by an individual or group of people. Based on the above, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or Global Goals was designed.

According to the United Nations (2015), the Sustainable Development Goals or Global Goals are collection of seventeen interlinked objectives designed to serve as a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity of people and the planet, now and into future. SDGs therefore, emphasize the interconnected environmental, social and economic aspect of sustainable development by putting sustainability at their Centre.

The sustainable Development Goals is aimed at ending poverty and inequality, protect the planet and ensure that all people enjoy health, justice and prosperity. Jeffrey (2015), noted that, SDGs is vital because: it encourage social mobilization; and create peer pressure among political leaders; spur networks of expertise, knowledge and practice into action. Therefore, SDGs is aligned with people, prosperity, planet, peace and partnership.

Records have it that, Nigeria adopted SDGs in year 2020 aimed at achieving the seventeen SDGs. According to Biemann, Frank, Hickmann, Thomas senit and Carole (2022) there are seventeen SDGs; which ranges from No poverty to partnership for the goals. Biemann et al (2022) noted that, Goal 1 and 2 are for ending extreme poverty and hunger by achieving food security and nutrition. It is the role of SDGs to contain among others massive expansion in the availability of work and the ability of individuals to secure an income to support themselves and their families.

Moreover, SDGs 6 (Decent work and economic growth) opined for, sustained economic growth, diversify innovative and upgrade for economic productivity, grading enterprises full employment and promote youth employment. This goal is synonymous with Business Education; which is for wealth and job creation.

It is vital to have effective Business Education programme in universities. According to Ritchie, Roser, Mispay, and Ortiz (2018), the SDGs number 4 was specific on quality Education to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. It equally stated that, the school buildings have access to electricity, the internets and computers. Again, there should

be affordable vocational (Business) and higher education. More importantly, an increased number of people with relevant skills for financial success. Looking at the SDGs critically, it can be concluded that, if there is any Education to achieve Sustainable Development Goals, it is Business Education.

Business Education is one of programmes offered in universities to equip the recipients with relevant knowledge, attitude and skills for classrooms and outside classrooms. Okoye and Achilogwu in Nwosu, Amobi and onyemaobi (2021) opined that, Business Education is a feasible element of education that introduces students to the development of demonstrable skills that could be further applied to economic and productive livelihoods. According to Chibuike (2019), Business Education exposes students to the world of commerce and industry and enable them to appreciate modern business activities. Moreover, Ugwuwoti (2022), opined that Business Education helps to equip the recipients with the right skills to engage in a life of work in the office as well as for self-employment. Nwosu et al (2021) highlighted, the objectives of Business Education to include to: develop basic skills for personal use in the future; acquire the basic knowledge and skills of Business Education; relate the knowledge and skills acquired for national development, develop basic skills in office occupation and prepare students with basic skills with which to start a life of work for those who may not undergo further training. The realization of the objectives of Business is largely dependent on the strategies applicable. Could it be institutional and Business Educators related strategies.

Institutional strategies are actions or plans that institutions (universities) take to achieve one or more of the effective Business Education programmes Chibuike (2013) noted that, if institutions that have the Business Education programme must achieve their goals, they must put in place quality enhancing strategies that will ensure the production of quality graduates for National development. Chibuike (2013) further outlined, such strategies to include adequate funding, review of programme, recruitment of quality staff and effective monitoring and evaluation. These strategies will ensure the achievement of sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme.

Another strategy that could achieve SDGs through effective Business Education programme is Business Educators (lecturers) strategies. A Business Educator is an expert in teaching Business Education programme particularly in universities in Nigeria. Ekoh-Nweke and Ezeabii (2021) noted that, Business Educator is an individual who has or obtained the professional qualification which enables him or her to be employed to lecture or teach in any recognized tertiary institution in Nigeria that offer Business Education programme and is physically fit, of sound mind and mentally alert.

Ugwunwoti and Eya (2020), stated that Business Educator is the implementer of curriculum, and decides on what instructional material to use, the methods to adopt, the amount of time to spend on each aspect and the equipment as well as space to use. In South-East states of Nigeria, Business Educators are employed by both the State and Federal Universities. State Universities are owned, financed and controlled by state government (Agbo and Ugwuwoti, 2022). On the other hand, Federal universities are owned, financed and controlled by the federal government. These Business

Educators irrespective of the ownership of the universities are expected to pursue effective Business Education programme.

Achieving effectiveness is the technique or mechanism put in place to bring about a degree of excellence of a product or services. According to Onyesom and Umoeshiet (2013), achieving effectiveness as applied to Business Education is the mechanism by which the propagators of Business Education programme ensure that the services they deliver or intend to deliver, serve the purpose for which it is intended and remains relevant and appropriate to the needs of the society.

There is no doubt that, with effective Business Education programme in South-East states, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is achievable. Regrettably, its recipients seem to be lacking the needed competencies (knowledge, attitude and skills). Could it be an absence of the desired strategies like institutional and Business Educators related? Upon this background, the need arose to determine the strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in south-East states of Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The major purpose of this study was to determine strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states and;
2. determine the Business Educators-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states?
2. What are the Business Educators-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states?

Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistic.

H01: There is no significant difference between the responses of Business Educators in Federal and State-owned Universities on institutional related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states.

H02: Business Educators in Federal and their counterparts in state owned universities do not differ significantly in their mean responses on Business Educators-related strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in South-East States.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. This design according to Nworgu (2015), is one which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people considered to be representative of the entire group. The population for this study comprised of 80 Business Educators from six universities offering Business Education programme in the South-East. There was no sampling, since the population was not large.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire (Achieving sustainable Development Goals Questionnaire. ASDGQ) developed by the researcher on a four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Business Education and one from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (measurement and Evaluation) all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT).

A reliability coefficient of 0.60 was achieved based on Cronbach Alpha procedure. A total number of 80 ASDGQ were administered on the respondents with 100% rate of return. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Decision on research questions were made based on the real limit of scale values 1 to 4 on a 4-point scale as follows: strongly Agree-3.50-4.00, Agree-2.50-3.49, Disagree-1.50-2.49 and strongly disagree-0.05-1.49. the null hypotheses were accepted where the calculated t-value was less than or equal to the t-table value at the appropriate degree of freedom; otherwise, the null hypotheses was rejected.

Results:

Research Question 1

What are the institutional-related strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states?

Table 1: Mean responses with standard deviation of the respondents on the institutional-related strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states.

S/N	Items on institutional-related strategies	Federal N=60		State N=20		Overall N=80		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
1	Encourage Business Educators to acquire relevant employability skills	3.50	0.69	3.31	0.71	3.50	0.70	Agree
2	Employment of adequate staff	3.44	0.66	2.75	0.77	3.10	0.72	Agree
3	Provision of study leave with pay to Business educators	3.23	0.79	3.21	0.75	3.22	0.77	Agree
4	Regular promotion of Business Educators	3.28	0.72	3.52	0.54	3.40	0.63	Agree
5	Organize periodic workshops for Business Educators	3.15	1.03	3.49	0.71	3.32	0.89	Agree
6	Develop disciplinary mechanism to correct unethical behaviour	3.20	0.79	3.12	0.82	3.16	0.81	Agree

7	Constant review of curriculum to ensure Entrepreneurship activities	3.30	0.73	3.19	0.75	3.29	0.74	Agree
8	Regular power supply in the institutions	3.20	0.79	3.12	0.82	3.16	0.81	Agree
9	Provide staff development annually for deserving staff	2.86	0.97	2.92	0.96	2.89	0.97	Agree
10	Engage in staff in exchange programme with other institutions locally	3.08	0.91	3.29	0.74	3.19	0.83	Agree
11	Regular payment of salaries and other incentives	3.60	0.66	3.52	0.77	3.56	0.72	Agree
12	Encourage oversea training for Business Educators for global competitiveness	3.20	0.73	3.19	0.72	3.19	0.73	Agree
Cluster mean/SD		3.25	0.79	3.24	0.82	3.25	0.81	Agree

The result in Table 1, above showed that items 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11 and12 with mean scores of 3.50, 3.10, 3.22, 3.40, 3.32, 3.16, 3.29, 3.16, 2.89, 3.19, 3.56 and 3.19 respectively have agree responses. This means that, Business Educators in Federal and State-owned universities were in agreement that institutional-strategies will help achieve sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in South-East states. The low standard deviation (0.81) shows similarity views of the respondents.

Hypotheses 1:

There is no significant difference between the responses of Business Educators in Federal and State-owned universities on institutional related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in South-East states.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State-owned universities on institutional related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in South-East.

Business Educators	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Federal	60	3.25	0.79	78	1.11	1.96	Do not reject Ho
State	20	3.24	0.82				

Table 2 shows that, the calculated t-table at 0.05 level of significance and 78 degree of freedom was 1.11; while the critical t-value under the same conditions, was 1.96. Since the calculated was less than the table value the null hypotheses was therefore not rejected.

This means that, Business Educators in Federal and their counterparts in state owned universities in South-East did not differ significantly in their mean responses on institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme.

Research Question 2

What are the Business Educators-related strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states?

Table 3: Mean responses with standard deviation of the respondents on the Business Educators-related strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East states.

S/N	Items on institutional-related strategies	Federal N=60		State N=20		Overall N=80		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
13	Related theoretical content to real Business challenges	4.40	0.60	3.50	0.71	3.95	0.66	Agree
14	Engaging students in work-based learning	4.42	0.55	4.50	0.60	4.15	0.58	Agree
15	Application of online teaching method	4.46	0.63	4.50	0.60	4.57	0.62	Agree
16	Exposing students to the current trend in the cooperate governance	4.54	0.54	3.52	0.63	4.03	0.59	Agree
17	Application of use technology in educating their students	3.46	0.50	3.53	0.51	3.50	0.51	Agree
18	Making innovative methods of teaching mandatory	3.45	0.76	3.41	0.70	3.43	0.73	Agree
19	Stimulate critical thinking in students	3.38	0.57	1.48	0.63	1.93	0.63	Agree
20	Coordinate internship programme for students	3.29	0.71	3.33	0.48	3.31	0.60	Agree
21	Exposing students to cooperative learning method	3.40	1.05	3.43	0.50	3.42	0.76	Agree
22	Regular attendance to classes	3.26	0.55	3.09	0.61	3.18	0.60	Agree
23	Invite successful entrepreneurs to talk to students	3.11	0.65	3.24	0.59	3.18	0.60	Agree
24	Integration of Business ethnics courses into Business Education curriculum.	3.59	0.62	3.61	0.58	3.60	0.52	Agree
	Cluster mean/SD	4.31	0.64	3.38	0.60	3.85	0.62	Agree

The result in Table 2 above showed that, items 13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23, and 24 with mean scores of 3.95, 4.15, 4.57, 4.03, 3.50, 3.43, 1.93, 3.31, 3.42, 3.18,3.18 and 3.60 respectively have agree responses. This means that, all the itemized were Business Educators-related strategies for achieving

sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in South-East states. The closeness of standard deviation shows the homogeneity of their responses.

Hypotheses 2:

Business Educators in Federal and their counterparts in State-owned universities did not differ significantly in their mean responses on Business Educators-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in South-East states.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State-owned universities in South-East states regarding Business Educators-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme.

Business Educators	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Federal	60	4.31	0.64	78	1.86	1.96	Do not reject Ho
State	20	3.88	0.60				

The result in Table 4 shows that, the calculated t-table at 0.05 level of significance and 78 degree of freedom was 1.86; while the critical t-value under the same conditions, was 1.96. since the calculated was less than the table value, the null hypotheses was therefore not rejected.

This means that, Business Educators in Federal and their counterparts in state owned universities in South-East states did not differ significantly in their mean responses on Business Educators-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme.

Discussion of findings

The findings in Table 1 showed that all the 12 items on institutional-related strategies are needed for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East States. Some of them of the strategies include regular power supply in the institution; provide staff development annually for deserving staff, regular promotion of Business Educators among others. The findings of the study were in agreement with Chibuike (2013) that, if institutions that have the Business Education must achieve their goals, they must put in place quality enhancing strategies that will ensure the production of quality graduates for National development.

The null hypotheses one tested on the institutional-related strategies revealed that, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State-owned universities on institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through

effective Business Education programme in South-East States. The findings of no significant difference indicated that the ownership of the universities had no significant difference in their opinions on institutional-related strategies.

The findings in Table 3, showed that the 12 Business Educators-related strategies would achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Business Education programme in South-East. Some of the items are: engaging students in work-based learning, relate theoretical contents to real Business challenges, application of online teaching methods, stimulate critical thinking in students among others.

The findings of the study, tallied with Ugwuwoti and Eya (2020), that Business Educator the implementer of curriculum and decides on what instructional materials to use; the methods to adopt, the amount of time to spend on each aspect and the equipment as well as space to use.

The null hypothesis with respect to Business Educators strategies showed that, the mean responses of Business educators in Federal and State-owned universities did not differ significantly on Business Educators related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in South-East States. The findings of no significant difference imply that, the ownership of universities in the South-East had no influence on their responses. Hence, the Business Educators-related strategies are needed for achieving sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme in the South-East.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the Business Educators in both Federal and State-owned universities in south-east were of the opinion that institutional and Business Educators related strategies achieve sustainable Development Goals through effective Business Education programme.

There was no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and their counterparts in State universities regarding institutional and Business Educators related strategies respectively.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion, it is recommended that:

1. There should be constant review of Business Education curriculum to meet global goals
2. Government at all level, should give adequate fundings to Business Education
3. Regular conferences should be organized to stakeholders based on SDGs
4. Authority concerned should encourage oversea training for Business Educators for global competitiveness
5. Business Educators should be given the opportunity to work in SDGs offices during annual leaves to enable them update their knowledge.

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